

Studies on Some Newer Possible Biologically Active Agents : Part II. Synthesis of N-(γ -aminopropyl)-2-heterocyclic-*p*- arylidene aminobenzenesulphonamides and N'(γ -amino- propyl)-2-heterocyclic sulphanilamides and their Antibacterial Activity

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Different heterocyclic sulphonamides and sulphanilamides have been synthesised and screened for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* against *E. coli*, *B. magaterium*, *S. typhi* and *S. aureus*. They were found to exhibit antibacterial activity.

SULPHONAMIDES are the drugs of proved therapeutic importance and are effective against various diseases¹⁻⁶. Ingle *et al* reported the synthesis of 2-sulphanilamido thiazole derivatives which were active against bacterial infection⁷. Arylsulphonamidostilbene disulphonic acid derivatives may also possess bactericidal and fungicidal activity⁸. Schiff's bases derived from sulphonamides are also good bacteriostatic agents^{9,10}.

In continuation of our previous work¹¹, we have extended our study towards the preparation of different substituted amines. These amines were synthesised by the direct addition of nitriles to the lithium aluminium hydride in ether or tetrahydrofuran with only limited hydrogen evolution. Further they were tested against four organisms viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus magaterium*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi* and were found to exhibit inhibitory effects against the above bacteria.

The IR spectra of N'-(γ -aminopropyl)-2-heterocyclic-*p*-arylidene amino benzenesulphonamides showed absorption in the range of 3200~3460 cm^{-1} with higher intensity and at 1600-1630 cm^{-1} due to -NH stretching and bending vibrations respectively. The respective asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of vibration of S=O appeared in the range of 1340-1300 cm^{-1} and 1170-1600 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Infrared spectra were determined in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The compounds were checked for their purity on tlc plates.

The key intermediates^{11,12} N'-(β -cyanoethyl)-2-heterocyclic-*p*-arylidene amino-benzenesulphonamides and N'-(β -cyanoethyl)-2-heterocyclic sulphanilamides were prepared and they were subjected

to reduction according to the procedure reported earlier in literature^{13,14}.

N'-(γ -aminopropyl)-2-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidyl)-*p*-benzalidene amino-benzenesulphonamide :

A solution of N'-(β -cyanoethyl)-2-(4, 6-dimethyl pyrimidyl)-*p*-benzalidene amino-benzenesulphonamide (4.20 g., 0.01 mole) in dry ether was slowly added with stirring to a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.4 g, 0.01 mole) in dry ether. The solution was refluxed for four hours. The excess of lithium aluminium hydride was decomposed with ethylacetate and its complex was decomposed by means of water. The solvent was distilled off and residual mass was crystallised from ethanol, m.p.190°, yield 3 g (70.4%). Analysis: Found: N, 16.33%; C, 62.30%; H, 5.81%. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires, N, 16.55%, C, 62.41%; H, 5.91%.

The compounds prepared according to this method are presented along with relevant data in Table 1.

N'-(γ -aminopropyl)-2-thiazolyl sulphanilamide

N'-(β -cyanoethyl)-2-thiazolyl sulphanilamide (3 g, 0.01 mole) in tetrahydrofuran was added to a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.40 g, 0.01 mole) in tetrahydrofuran at a rate to produce gentle refluxing. After refluxing for five hours the excess of hydride was decomposed by successive addition of water and sodium hydroxide solution. The granular precipitate formed was separated and the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The solid mass left behind was crystallised with ethanol, m.p.125°, yield 2.0 g (66.00%). Analysis: Found: N, 17.73%; C, 46.00%; H, 5.00%. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ requires: N, 17.95%; C, 46.15%; H, 5.12%.

The other compounds of the series were similarly prepared and the results are given in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 1—N'-(γ -AMINOPROPYL)-2-HETEROCYCLIC-P-ARYLIDENE AMINOBENZENESULPHONAMIDES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula*	M.P. °C	Yield %	Antibacterial Activity†			
						<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. magaterium</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1.	4,6-dimethyl-pyrimidyl	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	190	70.40	+	-	+	++
2.	"	<i>p</i> -OH	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	250	67.50	-	+	+	-
3.	"	<i>o</i> -OH	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	268	61.00	+	+	-	+
4.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	252	60.00	+	+++	++	+
5.	"	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	150	64.00	+	-	+	+
6.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ CONH	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	195	72.30	+	+	-	-
7.	4-methyl-pyrimidyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	155	74.00	-	++	+	+
8.	"	<i>p</i> -OH	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	235	69.00	+	-	-	+
9.	"	<i>o</i> -OH	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	250	74.00	-	++	++	+
10.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	232-233	77.00	++	+++	+	++
11.	4-methyl-pyrimidyl	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	239-240	66.00	+	-	-	+
12.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ CONH	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	248-249	75.00	+	-	+	+
13.	Thiazolyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	190-191	69.00	-	+	+	++
14.	"	<i>p</i> -OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	165	71.00	+	+	-	-
15.	"	<i>o</i> -OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	170	67.00	+	+	-	-
16.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	232	69.00	+	+	++	+++
17.	"	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	241-242	67.00	-	-	-	+
18.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ CONH	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	215-216	72.00	+	+	-	-

* Elemental analysis (C,H,N) were within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the theoretical value.

† - = No inhibition ; + = Zone size 6-8 mm ; ++ = Zone size 8-10 mm ; +++ = Zone size greater than 10 mm.

TABLE 2—N'-(γ -AMINOPROPYL)-2-HETEROCYCLIC SULPHANILAMIDES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula*	M.P. °C	Yield %	Antibacterial activity†			
						<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. magaterium</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1.	γ -aminopropyl	H	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	148-149	71.00	+	+	-	-
2.	γ -aminopropyl	acetyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	138	68.00	+	+	-	+
3.	Pyridyl	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	170-171	66.00	+	+	++	+
4.	Thiazolyl	H	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	125	66.00	+	+	+	-
5.	Pyrimidyl	H	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	200	59.00	-	-	+	+
6.	4-methylpyrimidyl	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	190-192	60.00	++	+	+	-
7.	4,6-dimethylpyrimidyl	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	150-151	70.60	++	+++	+	-
8.	Methoxy-pyridazyl	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	245-246	73.00	-	-	+	-
9.	Thiazolyl	phthalyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	210	75.00	+	+	-	-

* The analysis of (C,H,N) are within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the theoretical value.

† - = No inhibition, + = Zone size 6-8 mm ; ++ = Zone size 8-10 mm ; +++ = Zone size greater than 10 mm.

TABLE 3—N¹,N⁴,N^{4'}-TRI- γ -AMINOPROPYL-2-HETEROCYCLIC SULPHANILAMIDES AND N¹,N^{1'},N⁴,N^{4'}-TETRA- γ -AMINOPROPYL SULPHANILAMIDE

Sl. No.	R	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	γ -aminopropyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S	156	72.00	21.00	20.77
2.	Pyridyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S	170	73.00	20.00	19.78
3.	Thiazolyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	155-156	65.00	19.72	19.59

Antibacterial Activity

The compounds recorded in Tables 1 and 2 were screened for their antibacterial activity against four different organisms viz., *E. coli*, *B. magaterium*, *S. typhi* and *S. aureus* by agar diffusion techniques^{4,5}.

The agar medium was inoculated with a 24 hour old culture of the test organism. Sterile filter paper discs (5 mm diameter) saturated with the solution of the test compounds (10 mg/ml in acetone) were placed on the nutrient agar plates after drying up the solvent. The plates were incubated at the

optimum growth temp. of 37° and the zones of inhibition around the discs were measured after 24 hours. The experiments were carried out in duplicate and the results of antibacterial activity cited in Tables 1 and 2, indicate a mean value.

Structure activity relationship

The results (Table 1) show that all compounds were found to exhibit antibacterial activity against one or the other type of bacteria. It seems that the introduction of electron donating groups decreased the antibacterial property whereas electron withdrawing groups increased the activity. *p*-Chloro-derivative of sulphonamides is most effective against all the four types of bacteria.

The results in Table 2 indicate that most of the compounds show inhibitory effects except methoxy-pyridazyl derivative. The N'-(γ -aminopropyl)-2-pyridyl sulphanilamide is effective against all types of bacteria.

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